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Meeting Venue

Senate Hall & Histology Department
Victor Babes University of Medicine and Pharmacy
2, Eftimie Murgu Square, 300041, Timisoara, Romania

TOPICS

Histology during the "third wave"

Research in histology
Young histologist perspectives

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OUR EXPERIENCE IN EXAMINATION ON ANIMAL TUMOR MODELS

**Dusan Lalosevic¹, Anca-Maria Cimpean², Ivan Capo¹, Dejan Miljkovic¹,
Milan Popovic¹, Pavle Banovic¹**

¹Department of Histology and Embryology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
²Department of Histology, University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Victor Babes" Timisoara, Romania

From the beginning of the 20th Century, scientific interest for animal tumor models has continuously grown. Early works confirmed tumorigenic effect of many animal viruses, parasites, chemicals like tar, smoke and many others. Influences of animal species and their immune status have also a great impact. Our laboratory at the Faculty of Medicine in Novi Sad introduced tumor models in teaching process for students on the bachelor degree and PhD level. We used models as spontaneous tumors in laboratory animals, chemically induced tumors, and transplanted tumors for demonstration of drug effects and some immune mechanisms in tumor biology. From spontaneous tumors we examined mice-mammary carcinoma, mice lymphoma, hedgehog ovarian carcinoma, and dog prostate hyperplasia. For chemically induction of neoplasia we used 4-NQO in mice and produced squamous carcinoma of the tongue. In the group of transplanted tumors, we used

Ehrlich carcinoma in mice and BHK 21C13 sarcoma in diverse species of hamsters and mice. Tested drugs were thalidomide, dexamethason, heparin, metformin, doxorubicin, podoplanin. At this moment, examination of favorable effects of immobilization stress on tumor growth is in progress. Spontaneous and chemically induced tumors need time for growth and their appearance is rare. Because of that, formation of experimental groups is very complicated. We conclude that model of BHK 21C13 cell culture induced sarcoma in Syrian hamsters is the best model, easy reproducible and without influence of host immune mechanisms.